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Ergonomic and Digital Interventions to Support Occupational Safety, Health, and Work Ability Among Older Workers

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ABSTRACT

Population ageing and extended working lives have increased the need to create safe and sustainable working conditions for older employees. This article examines the impact of ageing on work ability, occupational safety and health (OSH), and workplace performance, with particular emphasis on ergonomic and organizational interventions supporting older workers. The study reviews current employment trends among older workers and discusses the role of age management, ergonomic workplace adaptation, and age diversity in promoting sustainable employability. Particular attention is devoted to digital ergonomics, including workplace simulation tools, virtual reality, and digital human modelling technologies. These approaches enable the assessment of physical workload, working postures, and occupational risks during workplace design and optimization. The review highlights the potential of digital ergonomic solutions to improve workplace safety, reduce physical strain, and support longer working lives. At the same time, the limitations of digital tools and the importance of integrating technological solutions with organizational measures and occupational health management are discussed. The findings suggest that effective support for older workers requires an integrated approach combining ergonomics, occupational safety and health, digital technologies, and age management strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Workforce ageing has become one of the most significant challenges facing contemporary labour markets and is increasingly reflected in the activities of international organizations such as the United Nations (UN), the World Health Organization (WHO), the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and Eurostat. As populations age, the proportion of economically active older individuals continues to increase, generating new demands in the areas of occupational safety and health (OSH), ergonomics, and work organization.

Ageing is a natural biological process whose progression varies considerably among individuals and is influenced by genetic, health-related, and environmental factors. Advancing age is associated with changes in both physical and cognitive capabilities that may affect work performance, resilience to

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workload, and the ability to adapt to working conditions. At the same time, older workers possess substantial professional experience, expertise, and organizational stability.

According to the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA), occupational accidents occur less frequently among older workers than among younger age groups; however, their consequences are often more severe. The most common incidents involve falls, musculoskeletal injuries, and accidents related to inadequately adapted workplaces, particularly in manufacturing, transportation, warehousing, and health and social care sectors. Consequently, ergonomic workplace optimization, workload prevention, and workplace health promotion play a crucial role in maintaining occupational safety and work ability.

Workforce ageing is particularly pronounced in Europe and Japan and is increasingly evident in China, where the proportion of employed individuals aged 55 years and older has steadily risen over recent decades (OECD, 2023; Eurostat, 2023a). In response, governments and employers have implemented measures promoting flexible working arrangements, lifelong learning, age management strategies, and ergonomic interventions designed to sustain the work ability of older employees (WHO, 2021; Eurofound, 2024). Research consistently demonstrates the positive impact of ergonomic interventions and age-inclusive human resource management on work performance and occupational safety (Ilmarinen, 2006; EU-OSHA, 2016).

Despite technological advancements and increasing digitalization, many occupations remain physically and psychologically demanding. Ergonomics therefore represents an essential tool for adapting working conditions to the needs of older workers. This includes the use of digital ergonomic tools capable of analysing work movements, postures, and workload in real time.

The objective of this article is to identify opportunities for applying ergonomic and digitally assisted solutions that support work performance, occupational safety, and health protection among older workers. The importance of high-quality working conditions is further emphasized by evidence showing that the ability to sustain employment over an extended period depends not only on individual capabilities but also on the quality of the work environment and work organization.

2. OLDER WORKERS

2.1 Legal and Conceptual Framework for Employing Older Workers

The term older worker is not uniformly defined within labour legislation. It is most commonly used to refer to employees aged over 50 or 55 years, or to workers possessing extensive professional experience and specialized expertise. However, assessments of older workers should not be based solely on chronological age but should also consider work ability, health status, psychological well-being, and adaptability to workplace conditions.

From an occupational safety and health perspective, job demands should correspond to the employee's functional capacity and should not impose excessive physical or psychological strain. Consequently, assessments of work fitness should be individualized and based on the specific requirements of the job position, working conditions, and the worker's health status.

To support longer labour market participation among older employees, it is essential to create conditions that encourage their continued employment. This approach is reflected in the concepts of active ageing and age management, which focus on promoting health, occupational safety, eliminating age discrimination, and supporting age diversity within organizations.

Age management encompasses measures such as lifelong learning, flexible working arrangements, workplace adaptation, occupational healthcare, career development, and managed transitions into retirement. The growing importance of these measures is linked to demographic ageing, labour shortages, and the need to preserve organizational knowledge and competencies.

2.2 Current Trends in the Employment of Older People

Over the past decade, employment among older individuals has increased by approximately one-fifth compared with 2009 levels. These increases have been more than four times greater than those observed among individuals aged 25–54 years. The rising labour market participation of people aged 55–64 years has been largely independent of educational attainment and has primarily resulted from efforts to maintain stable full-time employment.

Statistical evidence indicates that most individuals leave the labour market shortly after receiving their first old-age pension. However, a minority continue working after retirement, suggesting a gradual transition from employment into retirement.

In 2023, the proportion of employed pension recipients remained relatively low. This finding suggests that delayed retirement is primarily driven by increases in statutory retirement ages rather than by a stronger preference among individuals to continue working after retirement. Eurostat data show that Estonia recorded both the highest employment rate and the highest proportion of employed pension recipients among individuals aged 60–74 years. Similarly, high proportions were observed in Latvia and Sweden. Employment rates among older people were also particularly high in Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania (Eurostat, 2023b).

By contrast, in Spain, Greece, and Romania, the proportion of employed pension recipients aged 60–74 years was below 1.5%, indicating a greater tendency for retirees in these countries to withdraw completely from the labour market rather than combine pension receipt with employment (Figure 1).

The topic of older workers has become increasingly important due to demographic ageing and the extension of working lives. Older employees contribute substantial professional experience, practical knowledge, responsibility, organizational stability, and loyalty to employers. They also play a valuable role in transferring knowledge and expertise to younger colleagues through mentoring and coaching activities.

At the same time, the employment of older workers presents several challenges, including health limitations, reduced physical capacity, difficulties adapting to new technologies, and persistent age discrimination. Consequently, support for lifelong learning, digital skills development, flexible work arrangements, and age management initiatives is essential. Intergenerational cooperation also plays a significant role by facilitating the effective integration of experience and innovation across different age groups.

In addition, several emerging trends are reshaping the employment of older workers, including the growth of the silver economy, increasing pressure to extend working lives due to demographic changes, and a growing emphasis on age diversity within organizations. The silver economy represents an economic sector focused on addressing the needs of ageing populations while simultaneously creating new opportunities for economic growth, innovation, and employment.

Figure 1. Employment Status of Individuals Aged 60–74 Receiving an Old-Age Pension, 2023 (% of Persons Aged 60–74 Years)

Note: Adapted from Eurostat, ad hoc extraction from the EU Labour Force Survey (Eurostat, 2023b).

Age-diverse teams are increasingly recognized as valuable because they combine the experience of older employees with the innovation and digital competencies of younger generations. Such teams support intergenerational learning, creativity, organizational stability, and collaborative workplace cultures. Although differences in work styles, technology adoption, and value preferences may sometimes create challenges, age diversity generally contributes to innovation, competitiveness, and the long-term sustainability of the workforce.

2.3 Physiology of Older Individuals and Work Physiology

Physiology is a biological science concerned with the functions of the human organism and the mechanisms that maintain internal homeostasis. Within ergonomics and occupational settings, physiological knowledge provides an essential basis for adapting working conditions to human capabilities. Work physiology, as an applied medical discipline, examines the functioning of the human body during work activities with the dual objective of protecting workers' health and supporting efficient job performance.

In the context of older workers, physiology focuses on age-related changes in the human organism and their effects on work ability, performance, and occupational safety. Physiological ageing is a natural biological process characterized by a gradual decline in functional capacity, although the rate and extent of this decline vary considerably among individuals.

Ageing is typically associated with reductions in muscular strength and endurance, decreased flexibility and motor coordination, diminished respiratory and cardiovascular capacity, slower metabolism, and deterioration of certain sensory and cognitive functions. At the same time, long-term professional experience, accumulated knowledge, and decision-making abilities are generally preserved and may even continue to develop.

These physiological changes should be considered when organizing work, designing working conditions, and implementing ergonomic workplace adaptations. Work physiology therefore contributes to the prevention of excessive physical and mental workload and supports the development of working environments that enable safe, effective, and sustainable job performance throughout the working life course.

2.4 The Impact of Ageing on Occupational Safety Among Older Workers

The ageing workforce represents a significant challenge for occupational safety and health (OSH). As working lives become longer and the European population continues to age, employers and policymakers face increasing pressure to adapt working conditions to the needs of older employees.

Among the most significant consequences of ageing are declines in physical capacity, deterioration of visual and auditory functions, slower reaction times, and a higher prevalence of chronic health conditions. These factors may increase susceptibility to occupational injuries and work-related strain. In addition, older workers may experience slower information processing and greater difficulty adapting to new technologies. Nevertheless, they frequently demonstrate high levels of professional experience, responsibility, and risk awareness, often resulting in safer work behaviour compared with younger workers.

From an organizational perspective, workforce ageing increases the need for ergonomic interventions, workplace adaptations, and support for intergenerational collaboration. European occupational safety policy emphasizes employers' responsibility to identify and manage risks that may threaten workers' health and safety, including risks associated with demographic ageing. Effective prevention requires continuous monitoring of working conditions and the implementation of technical, organizational, medical, and psychosocial measures designed to support work ability across all age groups (Král, 2018).

Table 1 summarizes the principal consequences of workforce ageing and corresponding preventive measures.

Table 1. *Effects of Ageing on Occupational Safety and Recommended Preventive Measures*

Area	Effects of Ageing	Recommended Measures
Physical capacities	Reduced flexibility, strength, and endurance; impaired hearing and vision; increased prevalence of chronic diseases; slower reactions	Regular health examinations; high-quality workplace lighting (intensity, colour, direction); lifting aids; ergonomic workplace design; workplace health promotion programmes
Cognitive capacities	More difficult adaptation to new technologies; slower processing of information required for work activities	Mentoring programmes; memory and cognitive skills training; simplified user interfaces; age-appropriate training methods
Safety	Longer recovery periods; less frequent but more severe occupational injuries	Improved safety signalling; injury prevention measures; reduction of high-risk tasks; targeted rehabilitation programmes
Social and organizational factors	More difficult adaptation to organizational changes; high reliability and experience; increased risk of fatigue	Flexible working hours; involvement of older employees as mentors; age management programmes; intergenerational cooperation
Productivity and adaptability	Potential reduction in work speed; higher quality and accuracy of work performance	Teamwork with younger colleagues; adjustment of work pace; task allocation according to competencies and capabilities

Note: *Adapted from Král (2018).*

2.4.1 Medical Fitness for Work Among Older Employees

In order to perform a particular occupation or job position, individuals must meet the required standards of medical fitness for work. This requirement applies equally to older workers. Fitness for work is assessed in relation to the content of the job, specific work tasks, and occupational requirements associated with a given position.

Medical fitness assessments are typically conducted through occupational medical examinations, including pre-employment, periodic, extraordinary, and exit examinations. To ensure consistency and transparency in evaluating health status, work limitations, necessary accommodations, and recommendations regarding suitability for specific positions, standardized assessment procedures and documentation templates are commonly employed.

For older workers, such assessments play a particularly important role in identifying potential limitations while simultaneously supporting continued labour market participation through appropriate workplace adjustments and preventive measures.

2.4.2 Optimization of Working Conditions and Risk Assessment

Visual working conditions represent an important ergonomic factor influencing both work performance and employee health. Insufficient lighting, inappropriate viewing distances, or inadequate visual conditions may increase eye strain, alter working postures, and contribute to musculoskeletal overload. Consequently, ergonomic workplace design should take into account workers' visual capabilities, task requirements, and the size of objects being observed (Smutná & Dulina, 2010).

When designing workplaces, particular attention should be paid to viewing distance, viewing angle, visual field, and object size. Frequently used tools and materials should be positioned within the optimal visual field to minimize unnecessary head and eye movements and reduce visual strain.

Equally important is the appropriate design of work surfaces and the overall ergonomic layout of the workstation. Workstations should allow individual adjustment according to workers' anthropometric characteristics, including adjustable work surface heights, seating arrangements, and the placement of equipment and tools. Inadequate ergonomic design may result in physical and psychological discomfort as well as long-term health problems.

As individuals age, certain physical and sensory functions gradually decline, making it essential to incorporate age-related considerations into workplace risk assessments and work organization. At the same time, older workers possess valuable experience, professional expertise, and strategic thinking skills (EU-OSHA, 2025). For this reason, organizations should support flexible work arrangements, ergonomic workplace adaptations, regular occupational safety training, and psychosocial support initiatives.

Ergonomically optimized workplaces contribute to reducing physical and psychological strain, preventing occupational injuries, improving productivity, and enhancing overall employee satisfaction. Moreover, they strengthen human reliability, which remains a critical factor in the safe and effective functioning of organizations.

2.5 International Comparison of Approaches to Older Workers

2.5.1 Global Perspective: Labour Market Participation of Older Workers

International comparisons of policies addressing older workers frequently focus on labour market participation rates and institutional conditions supporting longer working lives. One of the most widely cited composite indicators in this area is the Golden Age Index (GAI) developed by PwC, which evaluates how effectively OECD countries utilize the economic potential of individuals aged 55–64 and 65–69 years (PwC, 2023).

The GAI is based on seven weighted indicators derived from OECD databases, including employment rates among older age groups, relative earnings of older workers, participation in lifelong learning, gender employment gaps, the prevalence of part-time work, and long-term unemployment rates among older individuals. The resulting composite score enables international comparisons of countries' ability to create conditions that support prolonged labour market participation.

According to the most recent edition (GAI 2023), countries such as New Zealand, Iceland, and Japan rank among the highest-performing nations, reflecting both high employment rates among older adults and supportive institutional environments for extending working lives (PwC, 2023). Additional comparative evidence can be obtained from the OECD Dashboard on Older Workers, which provides harmonized indicators related to employment, job quality, and employability (OECD, 2023).

It should be noted, however, that the GAI primarily captures labour market outcomes at the macroeconomic level and pays comparatively less attention to working conditions and ergonomic aspects of employment.

2.5.2 European Context: Employment, Working Conditions, and Institutional Frameworks

Within Europe, substantial differences exist in the employment rates of individuals aged 55–64 years. Eurostat data indicate that Northern and Western European countries generally achieve higher employment rates among older workers than Southern European countries and several Central and Eastern European states (Eurostat, 2023a).

Employment rates alone, however, provide only a partial understanding of the situation of older workers. Working conditions, job quality, and institutional support mechanisms are equally important. Analyses conducted by Eurofound demonstrate that extended working lives are strongly associated with age-friendly workplaces, flexible work arrangements, opportunities for lifelong learning, and preventive occupational health measures (Eurofound, 2024).

A broader framework for assessing active ageing in Europe is provided by the Active Ageing Index (AAI), developed jointly by the European Commission and the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE). The AAI comprises 22 indicators grouped into four domains:

- Employment;
- Participation in society;
- Independent, healthy, and secure living;
- Capacity and enabling environment for active ageing.

The index therefore provides a multidimensional assessment of conditions that allow older individuals to remain economically and socially active (UNECE & European Commission, n.d.).

From an ergonomics research perspective, a particularly valuable feature of the Active Ageing Index is its differentiation of employment indicators across age groups (55–59, 60–64, 65–69, and 70–74 years). This enables a more detailed analysis of transitions between different stages of working life and retirement (UNECE & European Commission, n.d.). At the same time, the index incorporates health, educational, and social dimensions that are essential determinants of sustainable work ability.

The most recent available wave of the Active Ageing Index (AAI 2020) confirms substantial regional disparities across Europe. Scandinavian and north-western European countries consistently achieve the highest scores, whereas southern and eastern European countries generally report lower overall values. These differences are attributable not only to employment rates among older people but also to broader determinants such as population health status, educational attainment, and institutional support for active ageing.

2.5.3 Implications for Contemporary and Future Ergonomics

A comparative analysis of international approaches reveals three key factors that characterize countries with higher levels of labour market participation among older workers:

- Supportive labour market policies, including flexible retirement pathways and measures aimed at preventing age discrimination;
- Age-appropriate working conditions, encompassing ergonomic workplace design, adaptation of workload, and flexible work organization;
- Lifelong learning and skills development, which help maintain employability and work ability throughout later career stages (UNECE & European Commission, n.d.).

Macro-level indicators such as the Golden Age Index primarily capture the outcomes of these structural conditions through labour market participation rates (PwC, 2023). By contrast, European policy analyses and multidimensional frameworks such as the Active Ageing Index provide insights into the institutional and social determinants underlying these outcomes (UNECE & European Commission, n.d.).

For ergonomics research and practice, it is essential to bridge these macro-level indicators with the micro-level realities of workplace conditions and individual work ability. The quality of the working environment remains one of the most important factors determining whether employees can safely and sustainably extend their working lives.

3. WORK ERGONOMICS AND WORKING CONDITIONS

Effective, safe, and health-promoting work performance requires the adaptation of working conditions, tools, and work environments to workers' capabilities and needs, particularly those of older employees. Ergonomic interventions include technical, organizational, and educational measures aimed at reducing excessive physical workload, awkward working postures, repetitive tasks, fatigue, and work-related stress. They also seek to eliminate adverse environmental factors that may negatively affect health and performance.

The quality of working conditions has a substantial influence on work ability, physical and psychological workload, stress levels, and safe work behaviour. Long-term exposure to inadequate working conditions may contribute to health problems, human error, occupational accidents, and even major incidents. Consequently, workplace optimization should be considered an integral component of organizational management at all levels.

Every work activity places specific demands on an individual's physical and cognitive capacities. Therefore, maintaining a balance between job demands and worker capabilities is crucial. An imbalance between these factors may result in stress, reduced productivity, and declining work performance (Malý et al., 2025).

3.1 Digital Tools Supporting Health, Performance, and Occupational Safety

Digital technologies designed to support health, performance, and safety include applications, sensor-based systems, wearable devices, and artificial intelligence solutions that collect and analyse data related to workers' health status, productivity, and exposure to occupational risks.

Examples include mobile applications for monitoring sleep quality, heart rate, physical activity, and mental well-being; productivity analysis tools; biofeedback systems; wearable sensors; and safety monitoring technologies. In the field of occupational safety and health, digital solutions increasingly include environmental monitoring systems, digital OSH training platforms, fatigue detection systems, and sensors capable of identifying hazardous behaviours.

Within ergonomics, computer-assisted technologies have become important tools for analysing workplace layouts, visual conditions, reach distances, and work movements. Simulation models and virtual environments make it possible to test alternative workplace configurations, optimize working conditions, and reduce health risks before a physical workplace is constructed or modified. The advantages of simulation include the possibility of experimentation, reductions in implementation costs, time savings, and improvements in design quality. On the other hand, simulation-based approaches often require considerable investment in software, data preparation, and specialist expertise.

A particularly significant role is currently played by virtual reality (VR) technologies and the broader concept of the digital enterprise, which facilitate the simulation of production processes, workplace design, and optimization of working conditions in accordance with ergonomic and safety requirements. These systems are based on workers' physiological and anthropometric characteristics and support the creation of safe, efficient, and individually adapted workplaces—an especially important consideration when employing older workers.

Modern software solutions enable users to define a wide range of parameters according to the intended analytical objectives. Typical variables include age, body height, body type, upper and lower limb space requirements, reach capabilities, biomechanical characteristics, visual conditions, and other ergonomic attributes. A particularly valuable feature is the ability to evaluate static and dynamic workload, including manual material handling conditions and lifting tasks.

Using specialized software tools, digital human models can be created and manipulated according to specified anthropometric characteristics. Among the most widely used systems are DELMIA, Tecnomatix Process Simulate (eM-Power), JACK, and ErgoMas. Figure 2 illustrates an example of ergonomic workplace planning using the ErgoMas software environment.

The system supports the ergonomic design of workstations and production cells integrated into production lines. Once one or more workstations have been configured, time studies can be conducted and work tasks subsequently simulated.

One of the most sophisticated software platforms currently available is DELMIA, which provides a comprehensive suite of digital 3D manufacturing solutions. Within DELMIA, ergonomics functions as a dedicated module supporting workplace design, workstation analysis, and assessment of work activities. Its primary objective is to understand and optimize interactions among humans, machines, and products. From an ergonomic perspective, these interactions are viewed as components of a dynamic and open system in which the human operator constitutes an integral element.

Figure 2. Example of the ErgoMas software environment (adapted from Smutná & Dulina, 2010).

Note. Adapted from *Metódy a softvérová podpora v priemyselnej ergonómii* by M. Smutná and E. Dulina, 2010, *Slovenská ergonomická spoločnosť*.

In this framework, the worker is regarded as both the decisive and potentially limiting component of the system, significantly influencing overall system behaviour and performance outcomes.

Digital ergonomics tools enable organizations to monitor ergonomic conditions throughout the workplace lifecycle. Their principal advantage lies in reducing the time required to achieve acceptable ergonomic standards and enabling validation during the design phase of new or redesigned workplaces.

Before ergonomic analyses can be performed, the workplace must first undergo a process of digitalization. During this phase, the essential characteristics of the real workplace are abstracted and transferred into a virtual model. This virtual representation subsequently serves as the basis for ergonomic studies and simulations.

A further step in comprehensive workplace digitalization involves modelling human work activities. Human models are adapted to reflect real individuals through the use of anthropometric databases integrated into digital enterprise software systems. Specific work tasks are then assigned to the virtual worker, enabling simulation of job performance.

Such simulations serve multiple purposes:

- visualization of work activities,
- verification of task duration,
- evaluation of ergonomic risks,
- support for worker training and workplace instruction.

Simulation is valuable not only for newly designed workplaces but also for existing workplaces undergoing optimization and continuous improvement initiatives.

Following completion of the digital workplace model, ergonomic studies can be conducted to evaluate physical workload, working postures, workstation dimensions, task requirements, and work cycle durations (Slamková et al., 2010).

For the assessment of physical workload and manual material handling, internationally recognized methods are commonly employed, including:

- NIOSH Lifting Equation for manual handling tasks,
- Snook and Ciriello Tables,
- RULA (Rapid Upper Limb Assessment) for repetitive activities,
- OWAS (Ovako Working Posture Analysis System) for evaluating working postures during manual tasks.

3.2 Benefits of Digital Ergonomics for Age Management

The integration of digital ergonomics into age management strategies represents a significant shift from reactive responses to health-related problems toward a systematic and preventive approach to managing work ability throughout an employee's working life. Digital technologies enable the analysis of physical workload, working postures, reach distances, force requirements, and repetitive movements before a workplace is implemented or a work process is modified. In the context of an ageing workforce, this predictive capability is particularly valuable because it allows organizations to identify potential risk factors that may have a disproportionately negative cumulative impact on older workers.

One of the principal advantages of digital ergonomics is its ability to model workplace scenarios while taking age-related changes in work capacity into account. Reductions in muscular strength, limitations in range of motion, and increased sensitivity to static or repetitive workloads can be incorporated into digital models through modified biomechanical parameters. This enables the comparison of alternative workplace designs and facilitates the selection of solutions that minimize long-term strain while supporting the maintenance of work ability among employees aged 50 years and older. In this respect, digital ergonomics contributes to extending working lives without requiring premature job reassignment or early withdrawal from the labour market.

Another important benefit is the support of evidence-based managerial decision-making. The visualization of ergonomic risks and the quantification of workload using standardized assessment methods such as RULA, OWAS, REBA, and NIOSH provide objective information for investments in technical modifications, work reorganization, or the implementation of assistive devices. Digital simulations also facilitate communication among engineers, ergonomists, occupational safety specialists, and organizational management by enabling a clear demonstration of how specific interventions influence workers' physical workload.

Digital ergonomics further supports a more individualized approach to workplace design. It allows simulations of adjustments in work surface height, optimization of handling spaces, and modifications of work sequences according to the specific anthropometric characteristics of employees. Such an approach is particularly important for older workers, among whom interindividual variability may be substantially greater than in younger age groups.

From the perspective of organizational ergonomics, digital tools also contribute to the planning of sustainable workload distribution within teams, the design of job rotation systems, and the assessment of task suitability for different age groups. In a broader context, digital ergonomics serves as a bridge between technical workplace design and strategic human resource management.

Overall, digital ergonomics significantly enhances systematic age management by integrating ergonomic prevention, technological planning, and long-term work ability management. However, its effective use requires expert interpretation of results and integration with additional tools for evaluating working conditions, employee health status, and organizational factors.

3.3 Limitations and Risks of Digital Ergonomics in Relation to Older Workers

Despite its considerable potential, digital ergonomics is associated with several methodological and practical limitations that must be taken into account when interpreting results and making decisions based on simulation outcomes.

One of the primary limitations is that most digital ergonomic tools rely on simplified biomechanical models and standardized anthropometric databases. These models are generally based on population averages and therefore do not fully reflect individual differences in health status, chronic diseases, cumulative occupational exposure, or psychosocial factors, all of which are particularly relevant among older workers.

Another limitation concerns the restricted ability of digital models to capture the dynamics of long-term and cumulative workload. For older employees, occupational risks are influenced not only by immediate biomechanical demands but also by the chronic nature of exposure, recovery capacity, fatigue accumulation, and interactions with non-work-related factors. Digital simulations typically evaluate individual work cycles or short-term scenarios and may therefore underestimate risks associated with prolonged work exposure.

There is also a risk of overestimating the precision and objectivity of digital outputs. Quantitative scores generated by methods such as RULA, REBA, or the NIOSH Lifting Equation may create the impression of definitive and objective evaluations, although they remain model-based calculations founded on simplifying assumptions. In the case of older workers, where individual differences in functional capacity may be particularly pronounced, simulation results should always be interpreted cautiously and supplemented by workplace observations, employee interviews, and relevant health indicators, such as the Work Ability Index (WAI).

A further limitation arises from the fact that many digital ergonomic tools were not originally designed with workforce age diversity in mind. Although it is technically possible to simulate reduced muscular strength, limited mobility, or other age-related characteristics, such adaptations often require expert intervention and manual parameter adjustments. Without these modifications, digital models may implicitly represent a younger, physically fit worker, resulting in a systematic underestimation of risks for older age groups.

Organizational and economic constraints should also be considered. The implementation of digital ergonomics requires specialized software, trained personnel, and sufficient time for model development and interpretation. For small and medium-sized enterprises, these requirements may represent a significant barrier to adoption, limiting the broader application of digital ergonomic tools precisely where support for older workers may be most needed.

Consequently, digital ergonomics should not be viewed as a standalone solution to the challenges associated with workforce ageing. Rather, it should be regarded as one component of a comprehensive strategy that combines technical interventions, organizational measures, occupational health promotion, preventive healthcare, and active communication with employees. Only through the integration of digital simulations with real-world workplace assessments can organizations effectively support the long-term work ability of older workers while minimizing the risk of inappropriate interpretation of simulation results.

4. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this review suggest several practical measures that can support the health, safety, and work ability of older workers:

- Conduct age-sensitive ergonomic risk assessments that consider age-related changes in physical and cognitive capacities.
- Adapt workplaces through ergonomic design, adjustable workstations, assistive devices, and appropriate workplace lighting.
- Utilize digital ergonomics and simulation tools to identify and mitigate occupational risks before workplace implementation or redesign.
- Promote lifelong learning and digital skills development to support adaptation to technological change.
- Integrate age management principles into occupational safety and health (OSH) strategies, including flexible work arrangements, mentoring programmes, and intergenerational knowledge transfer.

These measures can contribute to reducing occupational risks, maintaining work ability, and supporting sustainable employment among ageing workers.

5. CONCLUSION

Population ageing and the extension of working life represent one of the most significant challenges for contemporary occupational safety and health systems. Maintaining the work ability, health, and productivity of older workers requires a comprehensive approach that integrates ergonomic workplace design, age management strategies, occupational health promotion, and organizational support mechanisms.

The findings presented in this study indicate that chronological age alone is not a reliable predictor of work performance or occupational safety outcomes. Although ageing is associated with physiological and cognitive changes that may affect work capacity, older workers continue to provide substantial value through their professional experience, decision-making skills, reliability, and organizational knowledge. Consequently, workplace interventions should focus on individual functional capacity rather than age itself.

The review further demonstrates that ergonomically optimized working conditions play a critical role in reducing physical and psychosocial workload, preventing occupational injuries, and supporting sustainable employability. In particular, digital ergonomics, simulation technologies, and virtual workplace modelling provide new opportunities for identifying occupational risks and evaluating preventive measures before their implementation. These technologies can contribute significantly to the development of age-friendly workplaces and support evidence-based decision-making in occupational safety management.

At the same time, digital ergonomic tools should not be regarded as standalone solutions. Their effectiveness depends on appropriate interpretation, integration with workplace risk assessments, occupational health surveillance, and active involvement of employees in the design and evaluation of working conditions. The complexity of workforce ageing requires a multidisciplinary approach that combines ergonomics, occupational medicine, human resource management, engineering, and organizational psychology.

From a practical perspective, organizations that invest in age-inclusive workplace design, lifelong learning, and preventive occupational safety measures are likely to benefit from higher workforce sustainability, improved knowledge retention, reduced injury-related costs, and enhanced organizational resilience. As demographic ageing continues to reshape labour markets worldwide, creating safe, healthy, and productive working environments for older workers should become a strategic priority for employers, policymakers, and occupational safety professionals alike.

Future research should focus on evaluating the long-term effectiveness of digital ergonomic interventions, developing age-sensitive assessment methodologies, and strengthening the evidence base linking ergonomic workplace design with sustainable work participation among ageing workers.

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Stanislav Malý serves as Deputy Director of the Research Institute for Labour and Social Affairs (RILSA), where he oversees the Occupational Risk Prevention Section, and also heads the Department of Ergonomics and Occupational Risk Prevention. He is a recognized expert in occupational risk prevention, ergonomics, human reliability, industrial safety, major accident prevention, and fire protection. With more than four decades of experience in occupational health and safety, he began his professional career in 1980 at the Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology (now the State Institute of Public Health). In 1990, he joined the Research Institute of Occupational Safety, v. v. i., which is now part of RILSA, where he has been actively engaged in research, expert consultancy, and the practical implementation of occupational safety and ergonomics principles. He graduated from the Faculty of Science at Charles University and completed his doctoral studies at the Faculty of Safety Engineering of VŠB–Technical University of Ostrava. Drawing on extensive experience in both research and academia, he also serves as a guarantor and supervisor of selected doctoral study programmes. Throughout his career, he has contributed to numerous national and international research projects, with a particular focus in recent years on ergonomics and work-related musculoskeletal disorders. He is a strong advocate of holistic and interdisciplinary approaches to ergonomics and occupational risk prevention, promoting the integration of human, organizational, and technical factors in creating safe and healthy workplaces.

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